
80. Neutron stars and pulsars

NEUTRON STARS are the collapsed cores of massive stars ($8 - 40M_{\odot}$), and they result from a supernova explosion. With radii of only some 10 km, but weighing in at about 1.4 solar masses, their densities, of around $10^{17} \text{ kg m}^{-3}$, correspond to those of atomic nuclei.

Pulsars are the rapidly spinning, highly-magnetised manifestations of neutron stars. They emit narrow beams of radio emission parallel to their magnetic dipole axis, seen as pulses at the object's spin frequency due to a misalignment of the magnetic and spin axes.

There are two broad classes: 'normal' pulsars are isolated objects with spin periods around 1 s. 'Millisecond pulsars' are old ($\sim \text{Gyr}$) neutron stars, spun-up during mass and angular momentum transfer from a binary companion; most known still have (non-accreting) binary companions, either white dwarfs or neutron stars.

Known pulsars (a tiny fraction of those thought to exist) number around 2600, with more than 80 msec pulsars in the Galaxy disk, and some 130 in Galactic globular clusters. The fastest spin-period is the 716 Hz (1.4 msec) eclipsing binary pulsar PSR J1748–2446ad in Terzan 5. The slowest, PSR J2144–3933, has a period of 8.51 s.

DISTANCES are important for understanding their physics (e.g. Jennings et al., 2018). They provide constraints on the nuclear equation of state (from their radii), and on energy transport in neutron star winds. Space motions point to their birth sites, while transverse velocities constrain the physics of supernova core collapse, as well as the evolution of close binary systems.

Precision astrometry is also crucial in determining accurate pulsar spin-down rates (via their luminosities) as well as their (relativistic) binary orbital decay rates (by properly accounting for the kinematic Shklovskii effect, and that of Galactic acceleration).

However, distances to neutron stars are difficult to measure. For most radio pulsars, they can be estimated indirectly through the observed pulse dispersion measure (the line-of-sight integral of the electron density), although this in turn relies on models of the Galactic electron density distribution.

Distances can occasionally be inferred from their association with star clusters, from spectroscopic parallaxes of binary companions, or from annual variations in pulse arrival times (requiring a timing accuracy of better than a micro-sec for distances of 1 kpc). Parallaxes can also be determined from astrometric imaging observations with VLBI at sub-milliarcsecond accuracy.

Incidentally, other than the Crab pulsar, examined in the context of Gaia DR2 by Fraser & Boubert (2019), and which I will discuss next week (essay #81) focusing on supernovae remnants, no pulsar is intrinsically bright enough at optical wavelengths to be visible with Gaia.

GAIA IS, however, contributing in the specific case of pulsar companions in binary systems, where the brighter orbital companion serves as a proxy, circumventing the problems otherwise arising from their small sizes and general lack of detectable optical emission.

The more than one billion astrometric solutions of Data Release 2 (2018) already included the binary companions to a number of known pulsars, including white dwarf companions to millisecond pulsars and the non-degenerate components of 'black widow' and 'redback' systems (msec pulsars with an ablating companion).

Jennings et al. (2018) worked with the 2424 (non-globular cluster) objects from the ATNF catalogue of known pulsars, selected the 188 in binary systems, and further restricted it to sources that could be securely cross-matched to the Gaia DR2 catalogue on the basis of their combined position and proper motion uncertainties. They found, finally, 22 counterparts in DR2, of which 12 have statistically significant parallax measures.

Amongst them are specific systems used in tests of alternative theories of gravity (PSR J0348+0432 and PSR J0337+1715), in theories of accretion (PSR J1023+0038) and of particle acceleration (PSR B1259–63).

Notwithstanding the fact that some pre-Gaia distance estimates are more precise (if not always more accurate) than those from Gaia DR2, they found a generally reasonable agreement between the previous estimates of parallaxes and proper motions with those from Gaia.

Taken together, the Gaia DR2 results already constitute a small but important improvement in the pulsar distance scale, with the subset of millisecond pulsars with Gaia distances helping to improve the sensitivity of pulsar timing arrays to nano-Hertz gravitational waves.

Their results also point to other areas that will be the subject of further detailed study. For example, the distances predicted by both favoured dispersion measure models (NE2001 by Cordes & Lazio 2002, and YMW16 by Yao et al. 2017) appear to be underestimated compared with those from Gaia, confirming earlier suspicions.

Their results on individual objects also identify areas in which several pre-Gaia binary and orbit models merit some revision and refinement. Thus for the nearby system J0437-4715 (actually one of the closest known neutron stars), the Gaia distance is only 77% of that derived from orbital derivative models, and is provisionally attributed to unmodeled binary reflex motion, which should be resolved with future Gaia data releases.

For J1417-4402, the Gaia distance lends support to the inference that its companion fills its Roche lobe, and disfavours the dispersion-measure distance (of 1.6 kpc). For J1816+4510, the Gaia proper motion disagrees with that from pulsar timing, requiring further investigation. For J2032+4127, the wide-orbit, long-period (46 yr) binary may have affected the Gaia astrometric fit, especially for the proper motion term. And for J2215+5135, the Gaia proper motion ($1.9 \pm 0.8 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$) is much smaller than the pre-Gaia estimate ($189 \pm 23 \text{ mas yr}^{-1}$), the latter now considered to be in error.

WHILE THE MAJORITY of massive stars have a stellar companion, most pulsars appear to be isolated. This implies that most massive binaries break apart due to strong natal ‘kicks’ received in supernova explosions. But since the monitoring of newly discovered pulsars has rarely been carried out for long enough to conclusively rule out multiplicity, the observed binary fraction can still be subject to strong selection effects. A study also based on Gaia DR2 to improve estimates of the binary fraction has been made by Antoniadis (2021).

Searching for companions to the 1534 pulsars with positions known to better than 0.5 arcsec, he found 22 matches to known pulsars, and eight new possible companions to young pulsars.

Examining their photometry and kinematics, he confirmed that the observed multiplicity fraction is small, even though the number of binaries in the DR2 sample below the sensitivity of Gaia and radio timing could still be somewhat higher. For example, he constrained the binary fraction of young pulsars to be below about 5%, and set an upper limit on the Galactic neutron star merger rate of 7×10^{-4} per year.

His results on individual objects, including new candidates, again point to areas in which pre-Gaia binary and orbit models merit further revision and refinement.

AS ALREADY NOTED, the accurate measurement of pulsar velocities provides important clues concerning supernova physics and the subsequent evolution of binary systems. In this spirit, Yang et al. (2021) also used Gaia DR2 to selected a sample of 24 young ($< 3 \text{ Myr}$) pulsars with accurate parallaxes, using them to measure the velocity of their local standard of rest and their local velocity dispersion (by selecting 20 or more Gaia stars within 20–50 pc of each selected source).

The median difference between their calculated local standard of rest and the local Galactic rotation model is 7.6 km s^{-1} , small compared to the typical velocity dispersion of 27.5 km s^{-1} . But for pulsars away from the Galactic plane, the differences grow significantly, up to 40 km s^{-1} .

More importantly, the fact that the stellar velocity dispersion in the vicinity of low-velocity pulsars is often comparable to their transverse velocities, confirms that the intrinsic velocities of neutron star progenitors must be considered when estimating their natal kicks, and their subsequent evolution.

WITH RESULTS TO DATE exploiting only astrometry based on Gaia DR2, and the contributions of Gaia’s distances and proper motions already having an impact on statistical studies and on the improved understanding of individual objects, much more in this area can be expected from future Gaia data releases.

